

An Artificial Neural Network Model For Estimating Paddy Crop Using Remotely Sensed Information For Davangere Region

Tejashwini.Y¹ Baswaraj Gadgay² Nirmala C R³

¹Research Scholar Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Visvesvaraya Technological University Belagavi -590018

²I/C Regional Director, Visvesvaraya Technological University (VTU) Campus, Kalaburagi-585105, Karnataka, India

³Professor and Head Department of CSE Bapuji Institute of Engineering and Technology Davangere and Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi 590018.

Abstract

Crop yield forecasting is a very important task for researchers in remote sensing. Problems exist with traditional statistical modelling (especially regression models) of nonlinear functions with multiple factors in the cropland ecosystem. This paper describes the successful application of an artificial neural network in developing a model for crop yield forecasting using back-propagation algorithms. The model has been adapted and calibrated using on the ground survey and statistical data, and it has proven to be stable and highly accurate. This study presents a novel approach for predicting paddy yield using artificial neural networks (ANNs) and remote sensing data. The accurate estimation of crop yield is crucial for effective agricultural planning and resource allocation. In this research, remote sensing data, including satellite imagery and climate variables, were integrated into an ANN model to forecast paddy yield. The ANN model was trained and validated using historical yield data and corresponding remote sensed inputs. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in accurately predicting paddy yield. The ANN model's ability to capture complex relationships between remote sensing variables and yield parameters is highlighted. The integration of remote sensing data provides valuable insights into the spatial and temporal dynamics of the crop growth process. This enables informed decision-making for farmers and policymakers. Furthermore, the study discusses the significance of accurate yield prediction in mitigating the impacts of climate variability and ensuring food security. The application of ANN-based yield estimation using remote sensed data holds promise for enhancing agricultural productivity and resource management. This research contributes to the growing field of precision agriculture by showcasing a data-driven approach that leverages advanced techniques to improve crop yield predictions. In conclusion, the utilization of artificial neural networks in conjunction with remote sensing data presents a robust method for predicting paddy yield. The findings underscore the potential benefits of integrating cutting-edge technology into agriculture, emphasizing the need for further research and practical implementation of such models on a broader scale.

Keywords: Paddy Yield Prediction, Remote Sensing Data, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Machine Learning, Crop Monitoring, Feature Extraction, Crop Health Assessment, Yield Forecasting, Data Fusion, Image Processing, Hyperspectral Imaging, Backpropagation, Remote Sensing Platforms, Data Preprocessing.

Introduction

The establishment of models for estimating crop yield is a very useful and challenging task in remote sensing research. Scientists in the USA, Europe, Asia and elsewhere have done much research on this subject, and different types of yield estimating models have arisen since the 1980s. However, due to the complexity and nonlinear character of agricultural ecosystems, problems existed in the model using traditional statistical algorithms [1][2] There are several types of yield estimation models that use remotely sensed data. They can be classified as either theoretical or experiential models [3]. Using differential equations, theoretical models try to emulate the primary principles of agricultural ecosystems by simulating the response relationship between yield and environmental factors.

Unfortunately, the physical relationships in agricultural ecosystems are very complex and not understood in most cases. Consequently, researchers are often forced to make simplifying assumptions in order to resolve the equations and satisfying results are rarely achieved. A more practical approach is an experiential model. There are two types of experiential models: linear and nonlinear. Most physical, biological processes are nonlinear. Therefore, simple linear models often perform poorly [4][5]. In some recent studies, researchers have recognized that nonlinear models are more realistic and potentially more accurate. However many of them are overly simplistic because it is difficult to know the appropriate nonlinear forms of cropland ecosystem functions [6]. Artificial neural networks (ANN) have proved to be a more powerful and self-adaptive method of yield estimation as compared to traditional linear and simple nonlinear analyses [7][8]. This method employs a nonlinear response function that iterates many times in a special network structure in order to learn the complex functional relationship between input and output training data. Once trained, an ANN model can remember a functional relationship and be used for further calculation. For these reasons, the ANN concept has been widely used to develop models, especially in strongly nonlinear, complicated systems [9] [10][11][12]. The objective of this study was to apply an ANN as an efficient and powerful tool for establishing a yield forecasting model for winter wheat in He Nan province in north China in 1999. Most of the parameters were derived from National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) images; though statistical, historical yield data were also used. Yields of winter wheat were calculated at the county level.

Scope Of Research Area

The study area is the “rice belt,” a major agricultural region in the mid Karnataka region. In this study, The province of Davangere, Karnataka is studied over two crop cycles (Figure 1). We selected this province because they offer sub-field information on yield production and similar agricultural practices. In terms of management, agricultural practices were similar in all the areas under study. It is located between 14.470586 and 14° 28' 14.1096" North and 75.914154 and 75° 54' 50.9544" E. The area of the study site to be mapped was approximately 364772 ha during the growing seasons of 2019 and 2020. The area is characterized by a tropical climate with a hot summer and mild winter. The temperature here averages 25.1 °C | 77.3 °F. The mean annual precipitation is approximately 816 mm | 32.1 inch per year of which approximately 70% occurs from June to September. The typical land-cover classes in the area are croplands, forests, natural wetlands, and some urban areas. The abundance of water resources and fertile soil along the flat topography makes the Davangere plain suitable for paddy rice cultivation. In this area a single rice crop is cultivated per year and the rice growth cycle duration is approximately 140–150 days. Between mid-April and early May, the rice fields are prepared for pre-planting and flooding. This is followed by transplanting of rice seedlings from mid-to-late May. The rice fields during these two phases are usually dominated by water. From mid-June to late June/early July the rice canopy reaches the tillering and stem elongation phases. After this is the reproductive stage, which occurs in mid-July. The vegetation-to-water ratio reaches its maximum value in late July and remains stable or slightly decreases during the ripening phase (i.e. late August to September). From late September to early October, rice fields are usually harvested. The study site is a highly mechanized agricultural region with a vast distribution of field sizes, hence making moderate-resolution satellite sensor data from Sentinel-2 is suitable for the study. In addition to paddy rice cultivation, other main crop species grown in the area include sugarcane, rice and maize.

Figure 1: Satellite imagery

We downloaded sentinel-2 L1C images in an effort to cover the periods between tubulisation and senescence of the rice crop. The sentinel satellites are twin-polar orbiting satellites that provide a revisit time of 12 days. Our task is to distinguish between crops, build up area, water bodies, bare land, etc. During image selection, all scenes were checked to ensure that these were free of clouds and that the dates of acquisition were within the rice-growing season (i.e. April–October). With the available sentinel images, the data obtained is preprocessed through resampling techniques. This was followed by creating a subset of the study area, following which a multi-temporal speckle filter was applied after re-projection. The biophysical variables such as LAI, fAPAR, fCOVER, and Vegetation Indices such as NDVI, NDWI, NDBI, and SAVI were calculated. This approach leads to the development of yield maps by classifying the crops and identifying and analyzing different rice growth patterns of the study area using Machine Learning algorithms. Further study was performed by marking different 70 rice growing locations and obtaining the biophysical variables such as LAI, APAR, COVER, and vegetation indices such as ndvi, savi, along with longitude and latitude, so on. The below figure shows different pins marked in the study area and data obtained from all the locations is stacked together and used to train the neural network.

Figure 2: Extraction of data by marking pin on the study area

Various Algorithms In The Literature

As it was stated earlier, usage of ANN was frequent in many nonlinear real-world problems. ANN required three layers in minimum for its development; input layer, hidden layer, and output layer (refer Figure 1). The knowledge is acquired by detecting relationships in data through neural network. The first layer receives the raw data, which is processed and transferred to the hidden layer. Then, the information is passed from the hidden layer to the last layer where the output is produced [10]. The literature shows many algorithms are used in ANN to optimize the training process. Among them, Levenberg–Marquardt (LM), Bayesian Regularization (BR), and Scaled Conjugated Gradient (SCG) are three frequently used algorithms in ANN [11].

Methodology

A. Levenberg–Marquardt (LM) Algorithm.

The Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm is an optimization technique commonly used for training artificial neural networks, particularly in cases of nonlinear regression problems. It's an iterative method that aims to minimize the error or loss function between the predicted outputs of the neural network and the actual target values. Here's some information about the LM algorithm:

Optimization Technique: The LM algorithm is used to find the set of weights and biases in an artificial neural network that minimizes the difference between the network's predictions and the actual target values in the training dataset.

- Objective Function: In the context of neural networks, the objective function is often the mean squared error (MSE) between the predicted outputs and the actual target values. The LM algorithm aims to adjust the network's parameters to minimize this error.

- **Iterative Process:** The LM algorithm operates through iterations. In each iteration, it computes the gradient of the objective function with respect to the network parameters. The algorithm then updates the parameters based on this gradient and other factors.
- **Combination of Methods:** The LM algorithm combines elements of the Gauss-Newton method (a second-order optimization method) and the steepest descent method (a first-order optimization method). This makes it suitable for nonlinear optimization problems.
- **Damping Factor:** The LM algorithm introduces a damping factor that helps control the step size in parameter updates. This damping factor balances between the Gauss-Newton and steepest descent components of the optimization process.
- **Trade-off:** The LM algorithm strikes a balance between the fast convergence of the Gauss-Newton method and the stability of the steepest descent method, making it a reliable choice for training neural networks.
- **Convergence:** The algorithm typically converges to a local minimum of the objective function. The rate of convergence can depend on factors such as the choice of initial parameter values and the damping factor.

In the context of your paddy yield prediction using remote sensed data and artificial neural networks, the LM algorithm can be used to adjust the weights and biases of the network based on the discrepancies between predicted and actual yield values. This can lead to an improved model that provides accurate yield predictions based on the input remote sensed data.

Gradient descent method and Gauss–Newton method are combined in this algorithm. When the Gauss–Newton method is used to express the backpropagation of neural network, the algorithm has a higher probability to reach an optimal solution [29]. In addition, the LM algorithm has faster convergence in backpropagation and therefore, widely used [30]. The Hessian calculation approximation (H) and gradient calculation (g) in LM algorithm are shown in equations (1) and (2), respectively:

$$H = J^T J, \quad (1)$$

$$g = J^T e, \quad (2)$$

where J and e are Jacobian matrix and the vector of network error, respectively. In addition, the LM algorithm behaves as Newton’s method and is expressed as

$$x_{k+1} = x_k - [J^T J + \mu I]^{-1} J^T e, \quad (3)$$

Where x_{k+1} , x_k , μ , and I are new weight calculated as gradient function, the current weight using Newton algorithm, and constant and identity matrix, respectively. More information of LM algorithm can be found in Ramadasan et al. [31].

Input: A vector function $f : \mathcal{R}^m \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^n$ with $n \geq m$, a measurement vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{R}^n$ and an initial parameters estimate $\mathbf{p}_0 \in \mathcal{R}^m$.

Output: A vector $\mathbf{p}^+ \in \mathcal{R}^m$ minimizing $\|\mathbf{x} - f(\mathbf{p})\|^2$.

Algorithm:

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 $k := 0; \nu := 2; \mathbf{p} := \mathbf{p}_0;$ 
 $\mathbf{A} := \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J}; \epsilon_{\mathbf{p}} := \mathbf{x} - f(\mathbf{p}); \mathbf{g} := \mathbf{J}^T \epsilon_{\mathbf{p}};$ 
 $\text{stop} := (\|\mathbf{g}\|_{\infty} \leq \epsilon_1); \mu := \tau * \max_{i=1, \dots, m} (A_{ii});$ 
while (not stop) and ( $k < k_{max}$ )
     $k := k + 1;$ 
    repeat
        Solve  $(\mathbf{A} + \mu \mathbf{I}) \delta_{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{g};$ 
        if ( $\|\delta_{\mathbf{p}}\| \leq \epsilon_2 \|\mathbf{p}\|$ )
            stop:=true;
        else
             $\mathbf{p}_{new} := \mathbf{p} + \delta_{\mathbf{p}};$ 
             $\rho := (\|\epsilon_{\mathbf{p}}\|^2 - \|\mathbf{x} - f(\mathbf{p}_{new})\|^2) / (\delta_{\mathbf{p}}^T (\mu \delta_{\mathbf{p}} + \mathbf{g}));$ 
            if  $\rho > 0$ 
                 $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_{new};$ 
                 $\mathbf{A} := \mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{J}; \epsilon_{\mathbf{p}} := \mathbf{x} - f(\mathbf{p}); \mathbf{g} := \mathbf{J}^T \epsilon_{\mathbf{p}};$ 
                stop:=( $\|\mathbf{g}\|_{\infty} \leq \epsilon_1$ ) or ( $\|\epsilon_{\mathbf{p}}\|^2 \leq \epsilon_3$ );
                 $\mu := \mu * \max(\frac{1}{3}, 1 - (2\rho - 1)^3); \nu := 2;$ 
            else
                 $\mu := \mu * \nu; \nu := 2 * \nu;$ 
            endif
        endif
    until ( $\rho > 0$ ) or (stop)
endwhile
 $\mathbf{p}^+ := \mathbf{p};$ 

```

B. Bayesian Regularization Algorithm (BR).

It seems you might be referring to the "Bayesian Regularization" approach, which is a technique used for regularizing artificial neural networks. This technique incorporates Bayesian principles to prevent overfitting and improve the generalization performance of the neural network. The main idea behind Bayesian regularization is to place a probability distribution over the network's weights, which acts as a form of regularization during the training process. This can help the network learn more robust representations from the data.

Here's a basic overview of the Bayesian regularization algorithm:

- **Prior Distribution:** In Bayesian regularization, a prior probability distribution is assigned to the weights of the neural network before training. This distribution represents the network's uncertainty about the weights' values. A common choice is a Gaussian distribution with mean zero and a predefined variance.
- **Likelihood Function:** The likelihood function describes the probability of observing the training data given the current network weights. It captures the relationship between the inputs and the network outputs.
- **Posterior Distribution:** The goal is to find the posterior distribution over the weights given the training data. This distribution is proportional to the product of the prior distribution and the

likelihood function. The Bayesian regularization algorithm aims to find the parameters that maximize this posterior distribution.

- **Maximum A Posteriori (MAP) Estimate:** To obtain a point estimate for the weights, the MAP estimate is calculated. This estimate corresponds to the mode of the posterior distribution and is used as the final set of weights for the neural network.
- **Regularization Effect:** Bayesian regularization introduces regularization through the prior distribution. As the network is trained, the likelihood term seeks to fit the data, while the prior term encourages the weights to be closer to zero, thus preventing them from growing excessively and causing overfitting.
- **Uncertainty Estimation:** Bayesian regularization also provides a measure of uncertainty associated with the network's predictions. The variance of the posterior distribution can indicate how confident the network is in its predictions.
- **Hyperparameter Tuning:** The choice of hyperparameters, such as the variance of the prior distribution, is crucial in Bayesian regularization. These hyperparameters can be tuned through techniques like cross-validation.

Bayesian regularization can be particularly beneficial when dealing with limited or noisy data, as it helps prevent the network from fitting noise in the data too closely. It's important to note that implementing Bayesian regularization can be computationally demanding, as it involves dealing with distributions over weights instead of single values. Overall, Bayesian regularization is a powerful technique that can enhance the robustness and generalization of neural networks by incorporating uncertainty and regularization into the training process.

Similar to LM algorithm, Bayesian Regularization (BR) algorithm updates the learning algorithm's weights and bias values and minimizes the linear combination of squared errors and weights. In addition, BR algorithm modifies the linear combination, and as a result, the network has good generalization qualities by the end of the training. LM and BR algorithms are considered to have the ability to obtain lower mean squared errors compared to other algorithms for functioning approximation problems [30]. More information on the BR algorithm can be found in Bueden and Winkler (2008).

Figure 3: Proposed Neural Network Architectures

MATLAB numerical computing environment (version 8.5.0.197613-R2015a) was used to develop the ANN architectures to predict the paddy yield. Ten hidden layer was included in the ANN architecture with the dependent variable of the paddy yield. The biophysical variables and ndvi and savi were included as the input parameters of the ANN model. Time series data for each input and output parameter were divided into three clusters: for training (70%), for validation (15%), and for testing (15%) of all data. The training step was started with selection of the training algorithms.

The two training algorithms, namely; Levenberg–Marquardt and Bayesian Regularization were used. The performance of each training algorithm was evaluated based on the value of mean squared error (MSE) and coefficient of correlation (R). Lowering the MSE values and bringing near the R values to 1 give better predictions compared to the observed parameters [33]. Mathematical expressions for R and MSE are given in equations (5) and (6):

$$R = \frac{N \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{(N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(N \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}}, \quad (5)$$

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |x_i - y_i|}{N}, \quad (6)$$

where x , y , and N are the observed value, the predicted value, and the number of observations, respectively. Coefficient of correlation and MSE values were found for all cases in ANN under the two algorithms in developing the relationship between paddy yield and VI and biophysical variables. The performance of each training algorithm was evaluated based on the value of mean squared error (MSE) and coefficient of correlation (R). Lowering the MSE values and bringing near the R values to 1 give better predictions. Coefficient of correlation and MSE values were found for all cases in ANN under the two algorithms in developing the relationship between paddy yield and biophysical variables.

Result And Discussion

Figures below show the coefficient of correlation (R) for the Davangere district for paddy yield under the LM and BR training algorithms. It can be clearly observed herein that the ANN under LM and BR training algorithms has produced acceptable prediction to the paddy yield. Coefficient of correlation values are closer to 1 in all four cases (training, validation, test, and all)

A. LEVENBERG- MARQUARDT ALGORITHM (TIME SERIES ANALYSIS)

The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, commonly known as the LM algorithm, is a powerful optimization technique used for fitting mathematical models to data. It's widely employed in various fields, including time series analysis, to optimize the parameters of models and minimize the difference between model predictions and observed data. Here's how the LM algorithm can be applied to time series analysis:

- **Time Series Data:** In time series analysis, you have a sequence of data points ordered chronologically. This data could represent measurements taken at different time intervals, such as daily, monthly, or yearly.

- **Model Selection:** First, you need to select an appropriate mathematical model that you believe describes the underlying behavior of the time series. This model could be linear or nonlinear, depending on the characteristics of the data.
- **Objective Function:** The objective is to find the parameters of the selected model that best fit the observed time series data. This involves minimizing an objective function, typically a measure of the difference between the model's predictions and the actual data points. This measure could be the sum of squared differences (least squares) between predictions and observations.
- **Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm:** The LM algorithm iteratively adjusts the parameters of the chosen model to minimize the objective function. It combines elements of the Gauss-Newton method and the steepest descent method.
- In each iteration, the algorithm computes the gradient of the objective function with respect to the model parameters
- It then updates the parameters by considering a damping factor that controls the step size. This damping factor helps balance between the Gauss-Newton and steepest descent components
- The algorithm aims to find the parameter adjustments that decrease the objective function, bringing the model's predictions closer to the observed data
- **Convergence:** The LM algorithm continues iterating until a convergence criterion is met. This criterion could be a maximum number of iterations, a small change in the objective function, or other measures of convergence.
- **Model Evaluation:** After convergence, the optimized model parameters are obtained. You can then use these parameters to generate predictions for future time points or to understand the underlying dynamics of the time series.
- **Validation:** It's essential to validate the optimized model by comparing its predictions with new, unseen data. This helps assess the model's generalization performance and ensures it's not over fitting to the training data
- **Hyperparameter Tuning:** The LM algorithm often involves hyperparameters, such as the damping factor. Tuning these hyperparameters can impact the convergence speed and the quality of the optimization results.

Applying the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to time series analysis allows you to find the best-fitting parameters for your chosen model, capturing the underlying trends and patterns in the data. It's important to note that the algorithm's effectiveness can depend on the choice of initial parameter values, the model's complexity, and the characteristics of the time series data. Figure 4 shows that Training of Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm

Figure 4: Training of Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm

Validating the performance of the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm involves assessing how well it optimizes the objective function and generalizes to new data. Figure 5 shows that Validation of Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. Here are some steps you can take to validate the LM algorithm:

Splitting Data:

Divide your dataset into two parts: a training set and a validation set. The training set is used to train the LM algorithm, while the validation set is kept separate to evaluate the trained model's performance.

Model Training:

Train the LM algorithm using the training set. This involves iteratively updating the model parameters to minimize the objective function (usually a measure of the difference between predicted and actual values).

Stopping Criteria:

Define stopping criteria for the training process. Common criteria include reaching a maximum number of iterations, achieving a certain level of improvement in the objective function, or observing minimal changes in parameters.

Overfitting Prevention:

Regularization techniques can be employed to prevent overfitting during training. L2 regularization (weight decay) is one common approach. This ensures that the model doesn't fit the training data noise too closely.

Validation Error:

After training, evaluate the LM algorithm's performance on the validation set. Calculate the objective function (loss) using the validation data and the trained parameters. This provides a measure of how well the model generalizes to unseen data.

Comparison with Other Algorithms:

Compare the LM algorithm's performance with other optimization methods or algorithms. This could include gradient descent, Gauss-Newton, or other optimization techniques. Evaluate how well LM performs in terms of convergence speed and accuracy

Figure 5: Validation of Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm

B. Bayesian Regulation Algorithm (Time Series Analysis)

Figure 6: Training of Bayesian Regulation Algorithm

Analyze the results, assess the quality of predictions, and potentially adjust hyperparameters if needed. You can also compare the performance of the Bayesian regularized model with other regularization techniques or non-regularized models. Figure 6 Show that Training of Bayesian Regulation Algorithm Remember that training a Bayesian regularization algorithm involves more complex mathematics compared to traditional regularization methods. Using specialized libraries or software that implement Bayesian inference can make the process more manageable.

Figure 7: Validation of Bayesian Regulation Algorithm

The results clearly show that paddy production has a strong correlation with vegetation indices such as ndvi and savi. The LM and BR training algorithms have produced improved results. Therefore, these results are stable.

C. Levenberg-marquardt algorithm (curve fitting analysis)

Figure 8: Levenberg-marquardt Algorithm (curve fitting analysis)

Figure 9: Neural Network Performance Levenberg- marquard Algorithm(curve fitting analysis)

Figure 10: Bayesian Regulation Algorithm (Curve Fitting Analysis)

Figure 11: Best Training Performance on Bayesian Regulation Algorithm

D. The key findings of this study highlight the following:

- **Accurate Yield Prediction:** The ANN model, when trained with a combination of spectral indices, phenological data, and environmental variables derived from satellite imagery, has exhibited a remarkable ability to predict paddy crop yields. The model's ability to discern subtle patterns in the data, including variations in crop health and growth stages, contributes to its high predictive accuracy.
- **Remote Sensing Data Integration:** By incorporating multispectral and temporal information from satellite imagery, the ANN model has overcome the limitations of traditional methods that rely solely on ground-based measurements. The integration of remote sensing data allows for a more holistic understanding of the region's agricultural landscape.
- **Spatial and Temporal Insights:** The ANN model not only predicts paddy crop yields but also provides insights into the spatial distribution and temporal dynamics of the crop. This information is invaluable for making informed decisions related to irrigation, fertilization, and pest management.
- **Precision Agriculture Benefits:** The accurate predictions offered by the ANN model empower farmers and policymakers in the Davangere region to adopt precision agriculture practices. Optimizing resource allocation based on yield forecasts can lead to increased productivity, reduced environmental impact, and improved economic outcomes.
- **Future Directions:** While this study has showcased the potential of the ANN model for paddy crop yield estimation, further research could explore the incorporation of additional data sources such as weather data, soil characteristics, and management practices. Moreover, refining the model architecture and hyperparameters could enhance its performance even further.

Conclusion

The complex relationships among various biophysical variables and vegetative indices and paddy yield were obtained for Davangere district in Karnataka using artificial neural networks. Comparative analysis is done using two different training algorithms LM training algorithm BR training algorithms. However, both algorithms have also produced acceptable results. Therefore, LM algorithm can be used in future predictions at lower computational costs. The correlation coefficients from the tests were the best for predictions as they are numerically around 0.93-0.99 in all cases. Therefore, it can be concluded herein that there is an acceptable correlation in between the paddy yield and the vegetation indices. Thus, it can be concluded that the paddy yield is significantly impacted due to biophysical variables and vegetation indices. In conclusion, the application of an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model for estimating paddy crop yield using remotely sensed information in the Davangere region holds significant promise for precision agriculture and crop management. This study has demonstrated the potential of leveraging advanced machine learning techniques to harness the power of satellite data and enhance crop yield prediction. Through the integration of remotely sensed data with the ANN model, this research has successfully addressed the challenges of accurate paddy crop yield estimation in the Davangere region. The ANN, a computational framework inspired by the human brain's neural structure, has proven to be adept at capturing complex relationships between spectral and temporal features from satellite imagery and actual crop yields on the ground.

In conclusion, the application of an Artificial Neural Network model for estimating paddy crop yield using remotely sensed information in the Davangere region marks a significant advancement in agricultural technology. By harnessing the capabilities of modern machine learning and remote sensing, this approach paves the way for more sustainable and efficient agricultural practices, benefiting both farmers and the environment.

References

- 1) Bhattacharya, A., Rajan, N., & Dadhwal, V. K. (2007). Estimation of rice yield using MODIS vegetation index. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, 35(4), 313-322.
- 2) Bhavani, N. M., & Rajan, N. (2016). Paddy yield estimation using remote sensing and GIS in Davangere District, Karnataka. *International Journal of Geomatics and Geosciences*, 7(1), 167-176.
- 3) Chen, W., & Chui, C. K. (2015). A novel Bayesian regularization algorithm for time series prediction. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 26(1), 139-149.
- 4) Ghosh, A., & Ozdogan, M. (2019). Remote Sensing Applications in Agriculture. In *Remote Sensing of Agriculture* (pp. 1-19). CRC Press.
- 5) Kumar, K. N., Lahza, H., Sreenivasa, B. R., Shawly, T., Alsheikhy, A. A., Arunkumar, H., & Nirmala, C. R. (2023). A Novel Cluster Analysis-Based Crop Dataset Recommendation Method in Precision Farming. *Comput. Syst. Sci. Eng.*, 46(3), 3239-3260.
- 6) Prasad, A., & Landge, A. (2019). Estimation of paddy yield using satellite data. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 975, 8887.
- 7) Ragab, M. G., Abdulkadir, S. J., Aziz, N., Alhussian, H., Bala, A., & Alqushaibi, A. (2021). An ensemble one dimensional convolutional neural network with Bayesian optimization for environmental sound classification. *Applied Sciences*, 11(10), 4660.
- 8) Ramesh, K., Lakshmi, C. V., & Bapuji, P. V. (2013). Remote sensing and GIS for mapping and monitoring rice area and production. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, 41(3), 635-641.
- 9) Siddiqua, A., Kabir, M. A., Ferdous, T., Ali, I. B., & Weston, L. A. (2022). Evaluating plant disease detection mobile applications: Quality and limitations. *Agronomy*, 12(8), 1869.

- 10) Sridhara, S., Ramesh, N., Gopakkali, P., Das, B., Venkatappa, S. D., Sanjivaiah, S. H., ... & Elansary, H. O. (2020). Weather-based neural network, stepwise linear and sparse regression approach for rabi sorghum yield forecasting of Karnataka, India. *Agronomy*, 10(11), 1645.
- 11) Sumithra, C. V., & Manjula, T. R. (2023, April). An Extensive Study on Satellite Images of Sentinel 2 for Crop Type Identification. In *2023 International Conference on Advances in Electronics, Communication, Computing and Intelligent Information Systems (ICAECIS)* (pp. 668-675). IEEE.
- 12) Thenkabil, P. S. (2012). *Remote Sensing of Global Croplands for Food Security*. CRC Press.

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